

p-Bis-(2-imino-4-thiazolidone-*N*²-yl) benzene and its Derivatives

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p-Bis-(2-imino-4-thiazolidone-*N*² yl) benzene has been prepared from *p*-phenylene-bis-thiourea and monochloroacetic acid. The thiazolidone has been condensed with different aldehydes and ketones. The arylidene-thiazolidones have also been brominated.

In search of potential biologically active compounds and new analytical reagents it was thought desirable to synthesise bis-thiazolidone, joined at their 2, 2'-positions through a benzene ring. The thiazolidone thus prepared has also been condensed with different aldehydes and ketones. In the present investigations *p*-bis-(2-imino-4-thiazolidone-*N*²-yl)-benzene has been synthesised by the method described earlier¹.

The parent thiazolidone (I), when condensed with aldehydes or ketones, contrary to our expectations, did not result in the synthesis of diarylidene derivatives. In other words, only one thiazolidone moiety at C₂ underwent condensation with aldehydes or ketones. Thiazolidone (I), when condensed with even excess of benzaldehyde (6 moles), led to the formation of monobenzylidene derivative. This inference was drawn on the basis of analytical data. At this stage it was considered worthwhile to have an additional proof of C₂-position of other thiazolidone moiety being free and it was done according to the following scheme:

1. Fajari and Rout, *this Journal*, 1954, 31, 701; Rout and Mahapatra, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2427.

Compound (II) was treated with diazotised sulphanilic acid; subsequent decomposition of the diazo compound formed with splitting of nitrogen yielded (III) which decomposed at 250°. (Found: S, 17.14. $C_{13}H_{12}N_4S_3O_3$ requires S, 17.46%). The assumption that sulphophenyl group is attached at C₃ in (III), is based on the reasonings advanced in our earlier communication.²

As the halogens confer fungicidal properties³ and as the introduction of bromine into thiazolidone⁴ and thiazole⁵ molecules augments the antibacterial as well as antifungal activities, bromine was introduced into thiazolidones. No substitution of C₃-H of thiazolidone moiety took place, confirming our earlier observations^{1,4}. The arylidene-thiazolidone furnished dibromo derivative on bromination which lent further support to the fact that monoarylidene derivative was formed when (I) was condensed with aldehydes or ketones.

The evaluation of bactericidal and fungicidal properties of these compounds is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Phenylene-bis-thiourea was prepared by boiling *p*-phenylenediamine hydrochloride with ammonium thiocyanate⁶, m.p. 227° (lit⁷. m.p. 220°).

p-Bis-(2-imino-4-thiazolidone N³-yl)benzene (I).—A mixture of *p*-phenylene-bis-thiourea (7.5 g.), monochloroacetic acid (8 g.) and fused sodium acetate (6 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (40-50 ml.) was heated under reflux on a water bath for 5 hrs. A precipitate was obtained on pouring the reaction mixture on cold water. The precipitate was washed with boiling water 3 to 4 times to remove sodium acetate and unchanged phenylene-bis-thiourea. A small amount of the desired compound was recrystallised from ethanol, yield 8 g. decomposing at 264°. (Found: S, 20.62; N, 17.94. $C_{12}H_{10}N_4S_2O_2$ requires S, 20.91, N, 18.30%).

Condensation of (I) with Benzaldehyde: Formation of (II).—Compound (I) (1.5 g.) and benzaldehyde (1.1 g.) were refluxed in glacial acetic acid (30-35 ml.) in presence of fused sodium acetate (2.6 g.) on an asbestosed wire gauge for 3 hr. The clear solution on pouring on cold water formed a deep yellow precipitate and after keeping overnight it was filtered and washed with water and then with ethanol; yield 80%, m.p. > 280°. (Found: S, 15.88. $C_{10}H_8N_4S_2O_2$ requires S, 16.25%). The properties and analytical data of the other condensation products are recorded in Table I.

Bromination of (II): Formation of (IV).—Compound (II) (0.8 g.) in chloroform (30 ml.) was treated with bromine (2 ml.) in chloroform (5 ml.) at 0-5° for about 2 hr. On removal of chloroform under reduced pressure at room temperature, a vermilion-coloured bromo addition compound was formed. On treatment with sulphurous acid and basification with ammonia, this substance provided dibromo derivative (IV); of compound (II) it decomposed at 274°, yield 75% (Found: Br, 28.49. $C_{10}H_8N_4S_2O_2Br_2$ requires Br, 28.88%).

2. Patnalk and Pujari, this *Journal*, 1957, **24**, 814.

3. Goldsworthy and Green, *Phytopath.*, 1939, **29**, 700.

4. Pujari and Rout, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, **14B**, 398.

5. Mahapatra, *Nature*, 1956, **177**, 938; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 988.

6. De Clement and Wehrlin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, **31**, 70; *Compt. rend.*, 1877, **88**, 347.

7. Billster and Steiner, *Ber.*, 1887, **20**, 229.

TABLE I

No.	R	% Yield	Colour	Decomp. temp.	% Sulphur Found	% Sulphur Req'd.
I. R ₁ = H						
5	(<i>o</i>) HO-C ₆ H ₄	74	Yellowish Orange	250°	15.94	15.61
6	Ph OH=CH	70	Orange	260	15.02	15.24
7	(<i>o</i>) Cl-C ₆ H ₄	65	Yellow	> 280	14.48	14.94
8	(<i>p</i>) Cl-C ₆ H ₄	64	"	"	14.54	14.94
9	CH ₃ CH=CH	62	Brown	"	17.46	17.87
10	(3,4) OMe; (OH)C ₆ H ₃	55	Yellow	"	14.32	14.54
11	(<i>p</i>) Me ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	70	Brown	"	15.14	14.64
12		65	Dark brown	"	16.48	16.66
II. R ₁ = Me						
13	Me	55	Grey	262	18.28	18.49
14	Ph	58	"	274	15.33	15.69
15	Et	50	"	264	17.49	17.78
16	Pr	50	"	270	17.22	17.11
17	<i>t</i> -Bu	45	"	265	16.32	16.50

Table II describes the properties and analytical data of other bromothiazolidones.

TABLE II
vide Structure IV

No.	R	% Yield	Decomp. temp.	% Halogen	
				Found.	Req'd.
18	(<i>o</i>) HO-C ₆ H ₄	70	258	27.68	28.06*
19	(<i>o</i>) Cl-C ₆ H ₄	75	> 280	33.52	33.21**
20	(<i>p</i>) Cl-C ₆ H ₄	75	"	33.04	33.21**
21	(3,4) OMe (OH) C ₆ H ₃	65	"	26.14	26.66*
22	(<i>p</i>) Me ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	70	245	26.46	26.80*
23		60	> 280	29.15	29.41*

*% of bromine.

** % of chlorine and bromine.

The author is thankful to Prof. S. M. Mukherji and Prof. M. K. Rout for their interest in the present work.